

1 **Long-COVID, muscle strength and physical activity: a bibliometric analysis**

2 **Long-COVID, fuerza muscular y actividad física: análisis bibliométrico**

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18
19 **Abstract**

20 SARS-CoV-2 or COVID-19 is a disease caused by a coronavirus that has had a major impact
21 on all spheres of the world's population, but with a special impact on the health of people who
22 have suffered from the disease. Although COVID-19 is no longer a global pandemic and is no
23 longer a health emergency, part of the population that has suffered from the disease continues to
24 suffer from different types of sequelae. This is the so-called long-COVID. For this reason, the aim
25 of this study was to carry out a bibliometric analysis of articles related to long-COVID and its
26 implication for muscle strength linked to physical activity. For this work, the databases of PubMed,
27 Scopus, Dialnet and SportDiscus were reviewed. The results obtained were processed with the
28 bibliographic manager Mendeley Reference Manager and the Microsoft Excel V. 16.75
29 spreadsheet for subsequent statistical analysis. A total of 31 articles were identified with no time
30 restriction given the topicality of the subject of this work. The year with the highest scientific
31 production on this topic was 2022 with 54.84% of the total selection of articles led by Spain, Italy
32 and Brazil. All the articles were of collaborative authorship between 4.47 and 8.00. It is concluded
33 that there is a need for more research work related to long-COVID and muscle strength.

34
35 **Keywords:** long-COVID; muscle strength; physical activity; health; physical exercise.

36

37

38 **Resumen**

39 El SARS-CoV-2 o COVID-19 es una enfermedad provocada por un coronavirus que ha tenido
40 un gran impacto en todas las esferas de la población mundial, pero con especial impacto en las
41 salud de las personas que han padecido la enfermedad. Aunque actualmente el COVID-19 ha
42 dejado de ser pandemia mundial y una emergencia sanitaria, parte de la población que ha padecido
43 la enfermedad sigue teniendo secuelas de distinto índole. Es el denominado long-COVID. Por ello,
44 el objetivo de este trabajo ha sido realizar un análisis bibliométrico de los artículos relacionados
45 con el long-COVID y su implicación con la fuerza muscular vinculado con la actividad física. Para
46 este trabajo, se revisaron las bases de datos de PubMed, Scopus, Dialnet y SportDiscus. Los
47 resultados obtenidos fueron tratados con el gestor bibliográfico Mendeley Reference Manager y
48 con la hoja de cálculo de Microsoft Excel V. 16.75 para su posterior análisis estadístico. Se
49 identificaron un total de 31 artículos sin restricción temporal dada la actualidad del tema de este
50 trabajo. El año con mayor producción científica sobre este tema fue el 2022 con el 54.84% de la
51 selección total de artículos encabezados por España, Italia y Brasil. Todos los artículos fueron de
52 autoría colaborativa entre un 4.47 y 8.00. Se concluye que es necesario un mayor número de
53 trabajos de investigación relacionados con el long-COVID y la fuerza muscular.

54

55 **Palabras clave:** long-COVID; fuerza muscular; actividad física; salud; ejercicio físico.

56

57

58 **Introduction**

59 In December 2019 in the city of Wuhan (China), a new outbreak of coronavirus was reported.
60 The World Health Organization (WHO) named this new disease as coronavirus 2019 (COVID-
61 19), which is an infectious disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus (World Health Organization,
62 2023); SARS-CoV-2 is a single-stranded RNA virus capable of infecting humans and other
63 mammals, which has an interaction of the viral capsid protein S and human receptor proteins,
64 mainly angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE-2) and transmembrane protease, serine 2
65 (TMPRSS2) that allow entry of the virus into host cells (V'kovski et al. , 2021), causing symptoms
66 of fever, dry cough, dyspnoea and pneumonia in its severe form that can lead to death (Thompson,
67 2020). In addition, it has a severe reduction in serum T-cells, CD4⁺ T-cells, CD8⁺ T-cells and β-
68 cells. Previous studies found that total T cells, CD4⁺ T cells or CD8⁺ T cells are lower than 800,
69 400 or 300/μl, respectively, and are inversely correlated with patient survival rate (Diao et al.,
70 2020; XU et al., 2020). In itself, COVID-19 spread rapidly globally, becoming pandemic in March
71 2020 and eventually producing several variants.

72 Long-COVID, also called post-acute COVID-19 syndrome (PACS), is a complex secondary
73 multisystemic condition comprising often severe symptoms following SARS-CoV-2 infection
74 (Greenhalgh et al., 2020). It is defined by WHO as the development of new symptoms 3 months
75 after the initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, with a duration of these symptoms of at least 2 months
76 without other explanation (World Health Organization, 2022). PACS can be subdivided into two
77 categories: 1) subacute or ongoing symptomatic COVID-19, including symptoms and
78 abnormalities present 4-12 weeks after acute COVID-19; and 2) chronic or post-COVID-19
79 syndrome, which includes symptoms and abnormalities persisting or present beyond 12 weeks
80 from the onset of acute COVID-19 (Nalbandian et al., 2021).

81 The five most common symptoms are: fatigue (58%), headache (44%), attention disorder
82 (27%), hair loss (25%) and dyspnoea (24%) (Cares-Marambio et al., 2021; *FAIR Health Releases*
83 *Study on Post-COVID Conditions* | *FAIR Health*, n.d.; Shah et al., 2021), but there are a variety of
84 other less typical symptoms reported including: cough, myalgia, chest and joint pain, mobility
85 problems, cognitive and mental disorders ("*cerebral fog*", memory loss), olfactory and gustatory
86 dysfunction, sleep disorders, depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, gastrointestinal
87 distress, wheezing, rhinorrhoea, sputum, skin rashes and palpitations (Ayoubkhani et al., 2022;
88 Davis et al., 2022; Davis et al., 2022), 2022; Davis et al., 2021, 2023; Xie et al., 2022). Less
89 common symptoms of pernio, chills, flushing, ear pain and visual impairment have also been
90 documented (McMahon et al., 2021; Stavem et al., 2021; Xiong et al., 2021).

91 One of the distinguishing features in subjects who develop severe manifestations of long-
92 COVID is not the extent of viral damage, but immune damage mediated by exaggerated
93 inflammation created by the "cytokine storm" (Coperchini et al., 2021; Fajgenbaum & June, 2020;
94 Sheth et al., 2020). This inflammation is advocated as one of the main factors associated with
95 muscle catabolism in patients with long-COVID (Akbarialiabad et al., 2021; Raveendran et al.,
96 2021). Furthermore, it has been shown to have a negative impact on several organs and body
97 systems, including skeletal muscle (Piotrowicz et al., 2021; Yong, 2021). In fact, more than 60%
98 of people with long-COVID reported fatigue, reduced mobility and muscle weakness (Huang et
99 al., 2021; Karaarslan et al., 2022). For example, Paneroni et al. (Paneroni et al., 2021) reported
100 muscle strength and physical performance outcomes in patients who recovered from COVID-19
101 pneumonia without any previous musculoskeletal problems. They found weakness in the biceps

102 (73 %) and quadriceps (86 %) muscles. The maximum voluntary contraction for quadriceps was
103 54% and for biceps 69% of the expected normal value. Similarly, another study (Andrade-Junior
104 et al., 2021) investigated muscle mass and muscle strength in patients with COVID-19 after ICU
105 admission. It showed a significant decrease in rectus femoris cross-sectional area (30.1 %),
106 quadriceps muscle anterior compartment thickness (18.6 %) and grip strength (22.3 %) during the
107 first 10 days.

108 In people with long-COVID, a continued decrease in lymphocytes and significant elevation
109 of neutrophils and inflammatory markers, including C-reactive protein (CRP), IP-10, monocyte
110 chemotactic protein 1 (MCP1), macrophage inflammatory protein-1 alpha (MIP1 α), tumour
111 necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), interleukin (IL)-1 β , IL-2, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10 and IL-17, and ferritin
112 (Evcik, 2023; Grifoni et al. , 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Malik et al., 2022; Mendoza, 2020; Ueland et
113 al., 2020; Ye et al., 2020). These proinflammatory cytokines are known for their ability to
114 negatively affect muscle protein metabolism through activation of catabolic pathways and
115 suppression of anabolism (Webster et al., 2020), 2020) and, over time, these proinflammatory
116 cytokines will lead to muscle fibre proteolysis, decreased protein synthesis and decreased ability
117 of satellite cells to proliferate and differentiate, and ultimately fibrosis (Disser et al., 2020; Silva
118 et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022).

119 The aim of this study was to carry out a bibliometric analysis of articles related to long-COVID
120 and its implication for muscle strength linked to physical activity.

121 **Means and Methods**

122 A bibliometric review was carried out using the databases of PubMed, Scopus, Dialnet and
123 SportDiscus, as they are databases of indexed articles specialised in the biomedical area at an
124 international level and are mainly in English. They were managed with the bibliographic manager
125 Mendeley Reference Manager. For the search, the following keywords and Boolean operators were
126 used:

127 ((long covid) OR (permanent covid) OR (post covid) OR (Post-COVID Conditions)
128 OR (long-haul COVID) OR (post-acute COVID-19) OR (post-acute sequelae of
129 SARS CoV-2 infection) OR (long-term effects of COVID) OR (chronic COVID))
130 AND (muscle strength) AND (exercise) AND (performance)

131 Only original peer-reviewed full-text articles were considered. To select studies for inclusion,
132 a review of titles and abstracts was conducted prior to examining the full text versions.

133 ***Inclusion criteria***

134 The articles included were all those that met the following parameters: 1) Articles, systematic
135 and/or bibliometric reviews; 2) Papers that refer to pathologies or rehabilitation of muscular,
136 functional strength or strength training in post-COVID patients; and 3) That the COVID sequelae
137 were: fatigue associated with cardiorespiratory endurance, sarcopenia.

138 ***Exclusion criteria***

139 All articles that did not meet the following parameters were excluded: 1) No reference to post
140 COVID or long-COVID; and 2) Letter to editors.

141 ***Data extraction***

142 Afterwards, a data collection process was carried out in Microsoft Excel for further
143 statistical analysis, where the following questions were answered:

144 Q1: What was the year, volume and number of publication?

145 Q2: In which journal is it published?

146 Q3: What is the title of the article?

147 Q4: What is the quartile, impact factor and indexation of the article?

148 Q5: What type of document is it?

149 Q6: What language is it published in?

150 Q7: What is the gender and country of affiliation of the first author?

151

152 **Results**

153 Based on the descriptor used as a search string in the different databases, of the 88 documents
154 linked to the long-COVID and after filtering with the elements of inclusion and exclusion in this
155 analysis, 31 articles related to the long-COVID and muscle strength were finally identified. Given
156 that the subject studied is quite current, the search in the different databases used was not limited

157 in time. It is evident that the highest number of papers were produced in the hardest years after the
 158 SARS-CoV2 pandemic, in the year 2021 with 9 published papers and 2022 with 17 papers (29.03%
 159 and 54.84% respectively). In the year when the WHO declared the COVID-19 virus a global
 160 pandemic, only one paper was produced (3.23%) while in the current year 4 papers have been
 161 produced, constituting 12.90% of the total production of published long-COVID and muscle
 162 strength papers (Figure 1).

163 **Figure 1**

164 *Distribution of publications per year*

173 In reference to the quartiles in which these documents have been published, there is a
 174 predominance of Q1 JCR quartiles over the rest, with 51.61%, followed by documents published
 175 in Q2 JCR journals, with 29.03% of the total number of documents analysed (Table 1).

176 **Table 1**

177 *Distribution of papers by JCR quartiles and year*

Years	Q1		Q2		Q3		Q4		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
2020	1	3.23								
2021	4	12.90	2	6.45	2	6.45			1	3.23
2022	8	25.81	6	19.35	2	6.45	1	3.23		
2023	3	9.68	1	3.23						

178 *Note.* n = frequency by year and quartile.

179 It should be noted that the journal in which most publications were produced was the
 180 International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, an Open Access journal of the
 181 MDPI publishing group, with a total of 5 publications in the years under analysis, accounting for
 182 16.13% of the production in this analysis.

183 In terms of the origin of the countries in which the research was produced, documents were
 184 published in 13 different countries, with Italy, Spain and Brazil standing out, producing 16.13% of
 185 the documents published in each of these countries (Table 2). A very high percentage of the
 186 documents, 96.77%, are published in English. Only one document was published in a different
 187 language, in Japanese.

188 **Table 2**

189 *Distribution of the documents by research country and year*

Country	2020	2021	2022	2023
Italy (n)	1	2	2	
Italy (%)	3.23	6.45	6.45	
France (n)			2	
France (%)			6.45	
Portugal (n)		1		1
Portugal (%)		3.23		3.23
United Kingdom (n)		2		
United Kingdom (%)		6.45		
Turkey (n)		2	1	
Turkey (%)		6.45	3.23	
Spain (n)			3	2
Spain (%)			9.68	6.45
Japan (n)			1	1
Japan (%)			3.23	3.23
Singapore (n)		1		
Singapore (%)		3.23		
Brazil (n)			4	1
Brazil (%)			12.9	3.23
China (n)			1	
China (%)			3.23	
South Korea (n)			1	
South Korea (%)			3.23	
Egypt (n)			1	

Egypt (%)	3.23
Mexico (n)	1
Mexico (%)	3.23

190 *Note.* n = frequency of documents per year.

191

192 As shown in Table 3, the selected papers were analysed according to the type of paper or
 193 research being described. Three types of scientific papers were distinguished according to the
 194 inclusion and exclusion elements of this analysis, differentiating between intervention research,
 195 systematic reviews and other types of research. Papers published with intervention research occupy
 196 the highest percentage in all the years analysed.

197 **Table 3**

198 *Distribution by document type and year*

Years	Intervention (n)	%	Systematic review (n)	%	Other type (n)	%
2020	1	3.23				
2021	5	16.13			4	12.90
2022	9	29.03	2	6.45	6	19.35
2023	3	9.68			1	3.23

199 *Note.* n = frequency by year and type of document.

200

201 With reference to the number of authors who sign the documents, it should be noted that none
 202 of the documents under analysis have a single authorship, being all the production in co-authorship
 203 or collaboration. The average number of authors per document ranges from 4.47 in 2022 to 8 in
 204 2020. Year by year, the number of authors signing the documents has grown (8 authors in 2020,
 205 56 authors in 2021 and 76 authors in 2022), with the current year 2023 having a total of 23 authors
 206 participating before the end of the year. Table 4 also shows the percentage of collaboration by year.

207

208

209

210 **Table 4**

211 *Distribution by authorship and year*

Year	Single author	% Single author	Collaborative papers	% in collaboration	M collaborative authors
2020			1	3.23	8.00
2021			9	29.03	6.22
2022			17	54.84	4.47
2023			4	12.90	5.75

212 *Note.* M = average number of authors.

213

214 In relation to the authorship and co-authorship of the documents analysed, it is worth noting
 215 that 64.52% of the authors participating in the different documents are women compared to 35.48%
 216 men. However, only one woman appears among the most productive authors with authorship
 217 and/or co-authorship of the 31 documents analysed. Once again, the years 2021 and 2022 are the
 218 years with the highest percentage of female authorship, with 12.90% and 38.71% respectively,
 219 compared to an average of 16.13% for men, and with a clear predominance of the University of
 220 Murcia as the institution with the highest number of affiliations. Table 5 shows the authors who
 221 have participated most in the authorship of the documents, their affiliation and their country.

222 **Table 5**

223 *Authors with the highest production of documents, their affiliation and country*

Autor	n	Filiación	País
Amaya Jimeno-Almazán	3	University of Murcia	Spain
Jesús G. Pallarés	3	University of Murcia	Spain
Alejandro Martínez-Cava	3	University of Murcia	Spain
Ángel Buendía-Romero	3	University of Murcia	Spain
Bernardino J. Sánchez-Alcaraz Martínez	3	University of Murcia	Spain
Francisco Franco-López	3	University of Murcia	Spain

Javier Courel-Ibáñez	3	University of Murcia	Spain
José Antonio Sánchez-Agar	2	University of Murcia	Spain
Mehmet Kaan Kıralli	2	Kartal Koşuyolu Yüksek İhtisas Eğitim ve Araştırma Hastanesi	Turkey
Stefania Costi	2	University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	Italy

224 *Note.* n = frequency of authored or co-authored projects.

225

226 **Discussion**

227 The aim of this work was to perform a bibliometric analysis of the scientific production related
228 to long-COVID and its implication for muscle strength linked to physical activity.

229 Since the emergence of COVID-19, numerous scientific papers related to COVID-19, post-
230 COVID-19 syndrome and physical activity have been published, including meta-analyses and
231 systematic or literature reviews. However, there have been no bibliometric analyses specifically
232 addressing long-COVID and the implication it has had on muscle strength in people who were
233 infected with COVID-19.

234 Zhang's research (Zhang et al., 2022) incorporated a bibliometric review in the Web of Science
235 and Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-Expanded) databases, setting a publication period from
236 1 January 2020 to 14 February 2022. It included 1331 of articles and reviews, showing that the
237 number of published studies had increased from 334 in 2020 to 932 in 2021; furthermore, of these
238 publications, 8548 authors published on COVID-19 and physical activity. Another review
239 (Wattanapisit et al., 2022) searched the PubMed database from the start of the COVID-19
240 pandemic until 26 February 2022. They included 1125 articles, showing that the majority of
241 articles (n = 709, 63.02%) were published in 2021, while the remaining articles were published in
242 2020 (n = 341, 30.31%) and 2022 (n = 75, 6.67%). The most frequent type of publication was
243 original or research articles (n = 678, 60.27%) and the least frequent was systematic reviews (n =
244 21, representing 1.87%). Similarly, the study by Ciuldim and colleagues (2022) searched the
245 SCOPUS and Web of Science databases in the years 2020 and 2021, without language restriction.
246 For the final analysis they included 2023 articles, of which 382 were published in 2020 and 1641
247 in 2021, representing an annual growth rate of 330%. Likewise, the review by Zhang et al. (2022)

248 focused on searching the Web of Science Core Collection database with cohort dates between 1
249 January 2020 and 9 April 2022, where they selected the 50 most cited articles on physical activity
250 and COVID-19, this study had no restrictions in terms of population, study type or language.

251 Regarding the journals with the most publications, the study by Zhang, Y., et al. (2022)
252 commented that, of the top 10 journals that published research articles related to COVID-19 and
253 physical activity, MDPI's International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health was
254 the most productive with 179 publications; it was also the journal with the highest impact factor
255 (IF) (IF = 3.39). In Ciuldim's (2022) review, the most published scientific journal was also the
256 International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, obtaining the highest number
257 of publications, citations and H-index. From Zhang's (2022) study, the 50 most cited articles were
258 published in 34 journals with an IF ranging from 1.76 to 13.80; in addition, the International
259 Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health was the journal with the most cited articles
260 (n = 10). It is worth noting that this same journal is the one with the highest scientific production
261 according to this bibliometric review, with a total of 5 publications accounting for 16.13% of the
262 publications included.

263 With regard to the distribution of countries that have published the most articles, out of the
264 total of 110 countries in Zhang's (2022) study, the top five countries with the most articles were
265 the USA (n=344), followed by the UK (n=168), Italy (n=137), China (n=130) and Spain (n=117).
266 Similarly, Wattanapisit's (2022) review showed that the top five countries include the USA as the
267 first country (n=176, with 15.64%), the UK (n=98, with 8.71%), Italy (n=93, with 8.27%), Brazil
268 (n=84, with 7.47%) and finally Spain (n=81, with 7.20%). In Ciuldim's (2022) analysis, the country
269 with the most research on physical activity and COVID-19 was the USA (n=832), followed by
270 Spain (n=604), Italy (n=519), the UK (n=473) and China (n=458). Finally, with respect to the study
271 by Zhang, F. (2022), the 50 most cited articles were published by authors from 34 countries, with
272 the USA contributing the highest number of articles (14), followed by Italy (11), England (9),
273 Canada (8) and Spain (8). This is in complete contrast to our review, where the top countries were
274 Italy, Spain and Brazil, producing 16.13% each. It is true that this bibliometric review focuses
275 exclusively on muscular strength, a term that is not specified in the other reviews, where only
276 physical activity is mentioned.

277 On the other hand, in relation to the institutions of affiliation, Zhang (2022) points out that the
278 institution with the most publications was Harvard Medical School, USA (21). It is worth noting

279 that in this bibliometric review he identified a similar number of scientific papers produced by the
280 University of Murcia, Spain (21) with 67.74 %. In Ciuldim's review (2022), the most productive
281 institutions were located in Brazil (n=7), Canada (n=2), United Kingdom (n=2), Vietnam (n=2),
282 Austria (n=1), Italy (n=1) and Taiwan (n=1).

283 Regarding authorship, Ciuldim (2022) showed that Deborah Carvalho Malta (Federal
284 University of Minas Gerais, Brazil) was the most productive researcher, co-authoring 16 studies.
285 André de Oliveira Werneck (University of São Paulo, Brazil) and Lee Smith (Anglia Ruskin
286 University, UK) shared second place, with a total of 15 studies each. A result that clarifies a point
287 previously addressed in our review, where 64.52% of the authors participating in the different
288 papers we included were women, compared to 35.48% men.

289

290 **Conclusions**

291 We conclude from this bibliometric review that more scientific research is needed to
292 specifically address the implications of long-COVID in patients who have suffered from the
293 disease in relation to muscle strength.

294

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